

Open Surgical Management of Grynfelt-Lesshaft Lumbar Hernia: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Lumbar hernias are rare defects of the abdominal wall, representing less than 2% of all ventral hernias. Most are located in the Grynfelt-Lesshaft triangle and pose a diagnostic and therapeutic challenge due to their rarity and anatomical variability. Diagnosis is based on physical examination and confirmed by computed tomography, which is considered the gold standard for characterization and surgical planning.

Case report: We present the case of a 63-year-old woman with a history of type 2 diabetes mellitus and well-controlled hypothyroidism, who presented with left dorsolumbar pain of four years’ evolution and a progressive mass in the lumbar region. Computed tomography revealed a posterior wall defect consistent with a left lumbar hernia of the Grynfelt-Lesshaft type. Open surgical repair with placement of a polypropylene mesh was performed under general anesthesia. The postoperative course was satisfactory, with no complications or recurrence during six months of follow-up.

Discussion: Lumbar hernias may be congenital or acquired, and their clinical presentation is variable. Surgical treatment is the gold standard, with both open and laparoscopic approaches proving equally effective when prosthetic reinforcement is used. In this case, open repair was appropriate given the anatomical characteristics of the defect and technical availability.

Conclusion: An individualized surgical approach with mesh reinforcement allows for a tension-free, safe, and durable repair. Proper clinical suspicion, imaging diagnosis, and surgical planning are essential to achieve satisfactory functional and aesthetic outcomes.

KEYWORDS: lumbar hernia, Grynfelt-Lesshaft triangle, open repair, polypropylene mesh, case report.

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INTRODUCTION

Lumbar hernias (LH) are rare defects of the abdominal wall, accounting for less than 2% of all ventral hernias, and thus remain an uncommon diagnosis for general surgeons.^{1,4} The first case was described in the 17th century when Paul Berbette reported a lumbar hernia in France in 1672, and later, in 1731, De Garengot made the first formal publication following an autopsy finding.¹⁰ In 1733, Jean Louis Petit

described the first case of hernia through the triangle that bears his name (inferior lumbar triangle), while in 1866, Grynfelt characterized the hernia that emerges through the superior lumbar triangle, known as the Grynfelt-Lesshaft space.²

Lumbar hernias are more common in men between the sixth and seventh decades of life, generally unilateral and with a

Open Surgical Management of Grynfelt-Lesshaft Lumbar Hernia: A Case Report.

left-side predominance. Among these, the Grynfelt-Lesshaft hernia accounts for up to 95% of reported cases.⁴

Regarding etiology, lumbar hernias are classified as congenital (10–20%) or acquired (80%). Among the acquired ones, approximately 25% are traumatic, usually associated with multiple rib fractures; up to 50% are incisional, mainly following urologic surgeries involving lumbotomy or orthopedic interventions; and about 25% are spontaneous. Clinically, this condition may present with nonspecific lumbar pain and a soft mass or protrusion in the lumbar region, which can be mistaken for lipomas or other soft-tissue lesions. Therefore, imaging studies—particularly computed tomography—are essential to confirm the diagnosis by identifying the defect in the posterior abdominal wall and its contents.^{1,4}

Current treatment for lumbar hernias is based on hernioplasty with the use of prosthetic material, through either an open or laparoscopic approach, both considered safe and effective. Due to its low incidence and anatomical variability, there is no universal consensus on the ideal surgical approach, so management should be individualized according to the type of hernia, patient characteristics, and surgeon experience.⁵

Given its low incidence, diagnostic difficulty, and limited reported surgical experience, documenting and analyzing new cases of this uncommon entity remains important. The objective of the present report is to describe the case of a patient with a superior lumbar hernia (Grynfelt-Lesshaft type) managed with open mesh repair, highlighting clinical, diagnostic, and intraoperative findings, as well as the favorable postoperative outcome.

CASE REPORT

We present the case of a 63-year-old mestizo woman from Mérida, Yucatán, Mexico, housewife, with a medical history of type 2 diabetes mellitus and hypothyroidism, both adequately controlled with pharmacologic treatment (metformin 850 mg every 12 hours and levothyroxine 75 µg daily). She had no history of prior surgeries or lumbar trauma. She denied smoking, alcohol, or illicit drug use. The patient maintained a balanced diet supervised by a nutritionist, with moderate restriction of simple carbohydrates and saturated fats, and engaged in occasional walking as physical activity. She lived with her husband and adult children, with good family and psychosocial support. There was no family history of musculoskeletal disorders, connective tissue defects, or relevant genetic diseases.

She reported episodes of left dorsolumbar pain for four years, described as stabbing and oppressive, exacerbated by physical exertion, prolonged sitting, and Valsalva maneuver. During the past year, she noticed a progressively enlarging mass in the left lumbar region, accompanied by pressure sensation, spontaneous growth, and worsening pain. Due to persistent symptoms, she sought medical evaluation.

Physical examination revealed, in the left lumbar region below the 12th rib, a protrusion approximately 7 cm in

diameter, slightly mobile and irregular, which increased with the Valsalva maneuver and reduced in right lateral decubitus. The overlying skin was intact, without inflammatory signs or discoloration. The remainder of the abdominal, neurological, and musculoskeletal examination was unremarkable.

Given the reducible lumbar protrusion associated with exertion, the main diagnosis considered was a left lumbar hernia located in the Grynfelt-Lesshaft triangle. Differential diagnoses included subfascial lipoma, chronic retroperitoneal abscess, soft-tissue tumor, and post-traumatic muscular eventration. An abdominopelvic computed tomography scan showed a posterior wall defect in the superior Grynfelt triangle with retroperitoneal fat protrusion, confirming the diagnosis of a left lumbar hernia. No bone or visceral abnormalities or contralateral hernias were found. There were no economic, linguistic, or cultural barriers to diagnosis or treatment.

The preoperative prognosis was favorable due to adequate control of comorbidities and absence of incarceration or visceral involvement, so elective surgical management was planned. Lumbar hernioplasty with mesh was performed under general anesthesia, with the patient in right lateral decubitus. A transverse infracostal incision was made, and dissection was carried out in layers until the roof of the Grynfelt triangle was identified, showing marked weakness and laxity of the fascia. A hernial sac containing retroperitoneal fat was identified and carefully dissected until the aponeurosis of the transversus abdominis muscle was exposed. The hernial defect, well defined, measured approximately 3 cm in diameter. The contents were released from adhesions and completely reduced. The edges of the defect were reinforced with tension-free 1-0 prolene sutures, ensuring no residual protrusion. A polypropylene mesh was then placed over the defect and fixed with 1-0 prolene, followed by conventional layered closure.

Postoperative analgesia consisted of intravenous ketorolac 30 mg every 8 hours for the first 24 hours, followed by oral administration. Cefazolin 2 g IV was given as single-dose perioperative antibiotic prophylaxis. The postoperative course was satisfactory, and the patient was discharged 48 hours later without complications. No intraoperative modifications or changes in strategy were required; mesh placement was indicated based on the anatomical location and defect size to minimize tension and prevent recurrence.

During follow-up at one, three, and six months, the patient remained free of recurrence, pain, or functional limitation. Her metabolic control remained stable. She reported significant pain relief and complete return to daily activities within six weeks postoperatively. Medical evaluation confirmed absence of recurrence, good mesh integration, and aesthetically satisfactory healing without local complications. From the patient's perspective, the outcome was satisfactory both functionally and cosmetically, with complete disappearance of preoperative pain. No infections, seromas, hematomas, anesthetic complications, or late adverse events

Open Surgical Management of Grynfelt-Lesshaft Lumbar Hernia: A Case Report.

occurred. The patient continues under follow-up without recurrence or residual symptoms.

Figure 1. Coronal reconstruction of an abdominopelvic computed tomography scan showing a defect in the left posterior abdominal wall at the level of the superior lumbar triangle (Grynfelt-Lesshaft).

Figure 2. Hernial defect located in the superior lumbar triangle (Grynfelt-Lesshaft)..

Figure 3. Repair of the defect with placement of a polypropylene mesh fixed with prolene sutures, showing adequate coverage and reinforcement of the thoracolumbar fascia.

DISCUSSION

A lumbar hernia is defined as the disruption of the thoracolumbar fascia at the insertion of the aponeurosis of the internal oblique and transversus abdominis muscles. Anatomically, the lumbar region is bounded superiorly by the twelfth rib, inferiorly by the iliac crest, posteriorly by the lateral edge of the sacrospinalis muscles, and anteriorly by the external oblique muscle. Within this area, two weak points are recognized: the superior lumbar triangle (Grynfelt-Lesshaft)

and the inferior lumbar triangle (Petit), each delimited by two muscular borders and one osseous boundary.^{1,2,5}

The Grynfelt-Lesshaft triangle, wider and deeper, has the 12th rib as its base, the internal oblique muscle as its anterior border, and the spinal muscles as its posterior border; its floor is formed by the transversus abdominis muscle, and its roof by the external oblique and latissimus dorsi. The smaller Petit triangle is bounded by the iliac crest at its base, the external oblique laterally, and the latissimus dorsi medially.²

Open Surgical Management of Grynfelt-Lesshaft Lumbar Hernia: A Case Report.

One of the most widely used classifications for lumbar hernias is that of Moreno-Egea, which divides them into four types and guides the surgical approach according to defect size, location, hernia content, and degree of muscle atrophy.^{2,3}

Lumbar hernias are rare entities that may be congenital or acquired. Congenital defects are usually small and well localized, though progressive enlargement may result in large hernial sacs. The most frequent contents are retroperitoneal fat or colon, though rare cases have included cecal appendix or spleen. Clinically, presentation is variable; most patients are asymptomatic, with only progressive asymmetry or bulging in the affected flank.¹¹ The constant clinical sign is a lumbar mass, sometimes associated with pain, which increases with the Valsalva maneuver.^{2,4,6} Incarceration intensifies symptoms due to visceral traction, with an estimated incarceration risk of 25% and strangulation risk ranging from 8% to 18%, representing a surgical emergency.³ Diagnosis is primarily clinical, based on medical history and physical examination, though it may be difficult in small hernias (<5 cm). In such cases, imaging studies are essential, with computed tomography being the method of choice for identifying the extent of the defect, its contents, and adjacent musculature, while ruling out differential diagnoses such as lipomas, hematomas, or abscesses.¹⁰

Surgical treatment is the standard of care, as lumbar hernias—whether primary or secondary—do not resolve with conservative management.⁴ Reported surgical techniques include open and laparoscopic (transabdominal or extraperitoneal) approaches, with selection depending on the defect type, size, location, and surgeon experience.^{6,10} Both approaches yield similar results when prosthetic materials are used. In a 2016 prospective study comparing open and laparoscopic repairs over a 14-year period, the laparoscopic approach demonstrated lower morbidity and a recurrence rate of only 2.9%.¹ However, for small, localized defects—especially those in the superior triangle—open mesh repair remains a safe, effective, and technically simpler option, particularly in settings without advanced laparoscopic expertise.

In the present case, the patient had a left lumbar hernia classified as type A according to Moreno-Egea, with a 3 cm defect, retroperitoneal fat as content, and no muscle atrophy. Thus, open repair with prosthetic reinforcement was the most appropriate treatment. The repair involved a transverse infracostal incision, reduction of the hernia sac, and reinforcement with a polypropylene mesh fixed with prolene sutures, achieving a favorable postoperative recovery and no recurrence at six months of follow-up.

The use of polypropylene mesh is widely recommended due to its low passive shrinkage, high elasticity, large pore size, and excellent tissue integration, which reduce inflammation and enhance mechanical strength.^{8,9,11} Recent studies, such as that by Kamlesh-Singh et al., have shown that mesh repair significantly reduces postoperative pain and recurrence rates,

with up to 0% recurrence at 12-month follow-up.¹ Recurrence rates after open tension repairs can reach 50–65%, in contrast to mesh-reinforced tension-free repairs, where recurrence is minimal. Therefore, tension-free prosthetic repair is considered the current gold standard for lumbar hernia management.^{6,7}

Lumbar hernias are uncommon conditions requiring a high index of clinical suspicion and detailed knowledge of regional anatomy for successful diagnosis and management. The present case highlights the importance of an individualized approach, the use of mesh to reinforce the defect, and appropriate postoperative follow-up to prevent recurrence. Furthermore, it contributes to the limited literature on this rare entity and supports that open prosthetic repair remains a valid, safe, and effective alternative when performed meticulously in well-selected patients.

CONCLUSION

Lumbar hernias are rare musculoaponeurotic defects, representing less than 2% of all abdominal hernias, most commonly located in the Grynfelt-Lesshaft triangle. Diagnosis requires careful clinical evaluation supported by imaging studies, with computed tomography as the gold standard for confirming the defect and planning treatment. Surgical repair, whether open or laparoscopic, should be individualized based on patient characteristics, defect location, and surgeon experience. The use of prosthetic material is essential to ensure a tension-free repair and minimize recurrence. Overall, an adequate clinical suspicion, timely diagnosis, and meticulous surgical technique are key to achieving satisfactory and long-lasting results.

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Conflict of interest: None declared.

Ethical considerations: The patient was fully informed about the diagnosis, procedures, and potential risks. Written informed consent was obtained for the surgical and anesthetic procedures as well as for publication of this case report, in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the institutional regulations of the hospital.

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